

Applying Value Engineering Function Analysis to the Process for Building Disassembly and the Recovery of Wood and Timber for Construction

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1 Introduction

Recovery and recycling of wood and timber products is an application of circular economy principles to the construction industry [1]. However, the construction industry has not yet widely adopted the principles. According to a recent European Union (EU) Commission report on the construction industry [2], only 29% of companies engage in any form of reuse or recycling of construction and demolition waste (CDW). Within CDW, wood is one of the best materials with respect to circularity [3]. Wood and timbers are renewable resources that can be recycled multiple times in multiple formulations for multiple building lifecycles. At its end of life, wood can be converted to energy through incineration.

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The specific circularity principles vary from industry to industry. Within construction, the circular economy is often described using ten “R” principles. These are described in the United Nations (UN) report [3, p. 4]. They are often listed in a hierarchy with recovery being the most basic form of circularity and each additional “R” level increasing circular value. Mrad and Frölen Ribeiro provide a definition of the ten “R” principles [4, p. 4].

- Recover: Material is incinerated to recover energy.
- Recycle: Material is processed to obtain new material.
- Repurpose: Using the discarded product or its parts for a different purpose.
- Remanufacture: Using abandoned parts for a new product with the same function.
- Refurbish: Updating or restoring an existing product.
- Repair: Repairing a product to continue its function.
- Reuse: Reusing a product discarded but in good condition and fulfilling its original function by another user.
- Reduce: Increasing the efficiency in product manufacture or use by consuming fewer natural resources and materials to make a product.
- Rethink: Enhancing product usage.
- Refuse: Removing functions to make products redundant.

These “R” principles form the basis for analyzing the value embedded in processes that are associated with the recovery and reuse of wood and timber from CDW.

2 Background

2.1 System Elements

The value engineering discipline seeks to optimize the perceived customer value as compared to the cost of a component or system. Value analysis is a core element of value engineering. When doing value engineering, the foundation of value analysis is the function analysis of a product or process [5]. Within the construction industry, value analysis is often used as a form of cost containment [6]. Through value analysis, unnecessary building components can be identified and eliminated to reduce costs. Value analysis has been used with various forms of construction. Heiza et al. [7] used value analysis with high-rise buildings as a problem-solving tool that contained cost and increased quality. The area of the world where value analysis is most commonly applied to construction projects is Asia [8]. In their study, Chen et al. found that although the value analysis application is highly variable, when used, it delivers excellent results. Gimenez et al. [9] highlight the benefit of value analysis at the time of the building design. Once the design is completed, the cost of changes often negates any benefit that could be realized from adopting value analysis recommendations.

2.2 *Element Interactions*

The recovery and recycling of wood from CDW is a focus of the advocates for circular economy adoption. “The greatest opportunity for improved circularity of wood in existing buildings is in the recovery, reuse and/or recycling of building demolition waste” [3, p. xi]. However, recycling wood from CDW is a complex business decision. There are many options for what to do with the wood [10]. The direct costs, logistics costs, and energy costs for each option frequently change. In addition, some of the options create potential revenue, and some of the options have permitting or other regulatory costs. A key CDW recycling subprocess is sorting and segregating different construction materials to determine what form of reuse or recycling is appropriate. This sorting can be done either manually or with automation [11]. However, there is a cost and purity tradeoff with the automation equipment. Wood waste that cannot be clearly identified and segregated can be used for filler in composite materials. However, the CDW wood is usually contaminated, and the mechanical properties of the composite material with that type of filler are inferior [12]. Another key for successful wood recycling is to develop an intentional process. Oliveira Neto and Correia found that an intentional reverse logistics plan contributed to the benefit from recycling [13].

3 Methodology

3.1 *Process Flow Diagrams*

Seven of the ten “Re” principles involve additional processing of CDW. Those seven are recover, recycle, repurpose, remanufacture, refurbish, repair, and reuse [4]. Each of these is the result of a process that starts with the wood elements of CDW and ends with that wood being in some state that creates new value. In addition, there is an eighth process that does not result in a new value. That process sends the wood products to a landfill for eventual decomposition. These eight processes can be represented with process flow diagrams. The process flow diagram starts with the generation of CDW and shows the steps required to complete each “R” process. The steps are shown in sequential order and are connected with arrows. Process flow diagrams create a visual image of a process that may take a long time and be spread across many locations.

Jahan et al. [14] created a high-level flow for the lifecycle of construction products that had five steps in sequence. These steps are (1) raw material extraction, (2) preconstruction, (3) construction, (4) renovation/demolition, and (5) end of life. The first two steps are associated with the initial fabrication of the construction products, and waste in those steps would be considered industrial waste, not CDW. The remaining three steps can and often do create CDW. For the purposes of this study, the starting point of the process flow will be the generation of the CDW, regardless of which step in the construction lifecycle the waste was created.

3.2 Value Engineering

The value engineering approach used in this study is based on the methodology recommended by the leading professional organization that provides certification in value engineering techniques, SAVE International. They recommend a value engineering process that starts with a function analysis using a Function Analysis System Technique (FAST) diagram. This identifies unneeded functions, missing functions, and prioritizes the existing functions. The identified functions become one side of a Function Cost Matrix. The other side of the matrix is the product architecture for a product analysis or the process flow chart elements for a process analysis. The matrix is used to create a functional value for each element.

Function Analysis System Technique (FAST) The FAST analysis is a method for identifying and organizing the functions of a product or process. Since this study is focused on the recovery and recycling of wood from CDW, the process perspective is used. The FAST technique starts by setting the boundaries or scope of the process being analyzed. Outside the process boundary on the left side is a higher-order function that normally reflects the ultimate purpose of the process. Outside the boundary on the right side are any causative functions or events that would initiate the process.

Within the boundaries are the functions or activities that occur within the process. On the left side are the primary function(s). These function(s) normally represent a final step in a process path. They are the outputs of the process. The primary function delivers the result of the process, secondary functions are enablers or enhancers of the primary function. One goal of a FAST analysis is to determine if there are more efficient ways to accomplish the secondary functions. If the primary function can be achieved without some of the secondary functions, those secondary functions should be eliminated since they are contributing little if any value.

When creating a FAST analysis, it is often helpful to navigate the diagram from left to right and then from right to left to identify any unneeded or missing functions. When going from left to right, the question “How?” is asked with each function to identify the preceding functions. When going from right to left, the question “Why?” is asked to understand the relationship with any succeeding function. Also, with each function, the question “When?” is asked to determine if there are other secondary functions that should be connected with each other. An illustration is found in Fig. 1.

Function Cost Matrix The functional cost matrix (FCM) combines the functions identified with the FAST analysis and the steps associated with processing CDW to identify the inherent value of each step. The format of the Function Cost Matrix is similar to that used with Quality Function Deployment (QFD) [15]. In the FCM, functions are listed across the top of the matrix and the process steps are listed down the side. In one variation of an FCM, actual cost values to accomplish each process step are allocated across the functions. A second variation of the FCM uses the QFD approach for analysis. In this case, the functions are prioritized using a scale of 1 to 5 with “5” being the highest priority. The process steps are then correlated to the

Fig. 1 FAST analysis template

functions based on how significantly they directly contribute to the functional performance. The correlations are rated as high, medium, low, or no correlation. Using the standard QFD approach, the high correlation is given a multiplier of “9,” the medium has a multiplier of “3,” the low has a multiplier of “1,” and no correlation has a multiplier of zero. These multipliers are used with the priority of the functions to determine a correlation score for that step/function relationship. The total score of a step reflects that step’s contributed value to the overall process. When using the QFD approach, the scores reflect a relative value between steps.

The perceived customer value or score of each step is then compared to the total cost for that step. If the cost is significantly higher than the value, consider redesigning the process to minimize the cost at that step. If the value is significantly higher than the cost, assess whether the method of accomplishing that step is fully meeting the customer quality expectations. If not, consider improving the performance of that step, even if it means spending more money to do that step well. Improving the performance of that step will increase the value of the entire process in the eyes of the customer. If the cost and value are approximately the same, the effort associated with accomplishing that step is appropriate.

4 Analysis

The analysis in this study is based on using information from other studies and reports created by the EU or UN. This is an analysis of a generalized model of the industry, not a specific company or case study. Therefore, the analysis provides relative values for the process steps, not absolute values. Absolute values will depend on the specific organizational capabilities, geographical location of sites, and the current regulatory environment for the region being studied.

4.1 Value Engineering

The process flow diagrams show an idealized view of the processes that result in the eight potential “R” dispositions of wood that are found in CDW. The steps are at a relatively high level. In many cases, when a company decides to adopt one of these processes, it will need to establish a set of detailed steps to accomplish the task described in this high-level step. The particular steps often depend on the construction site and the organization’s infrastructure and capabilities. For instance, depending on site locations, shipping waste to an incinerator may be a short haul by truck or a long haul involving rail shipments and multiple trucks. For this reason, it is impossible to set exact detailed steps that apply in every case. The process map is found in Fig. 2.

The process starts with the creation of CDW during construction or deconstruction. A decision is made to recover the wood and use it again in the construction of another building or to allow it to be transformed into another product, material, or physical state. If it will not be used for production, it must be shipped to the appropriate facility and either dumped in a landfill or processed to be transformed into energy, a different composite material, or a different fiber-based product that is not used in construction. If it is to be reused in construction, then a decision is made concerning how it is to be used. If no modification is required, once it is inspected, it is sent to an appropriate distribution channel for resale. If modifications are required, then it must be sent to the correct facility. Often minor repairs can be made at the point where the sorting occurs. An example would be to trim a beam to a shorter length and remove an end that was compromised during demolition. That beam can then be inspected and returned to the supply chain. In some cases, the modification may be more extensive, so the wood is sent to a manufacturing facility to be refurbished into construction materials. Again, once inspected, it can be returned to the supply chain.

Fig. 2 Process map for CDW waste recovery and disposition

4.2 FAST Analysis

The FAST analysis of wood recovered from CDW is somewhat complex. There are two higher-order functions that are mutually exclusive. One is the reintroduction of the wood items into the construction supply chain. The other is the transformation of the wood into another form. A specific wood item could go through the first higher-order function many times throughout its lifecycle. However, once it has been transformed, it is no longer possible for it to be a wood element in construction so it will not be CDW. In fact, depending on the transformation, it may not exist at all.

Since there are two higher order functions, there are two FAST analysis diagrams. Figure 3 is the diagram for wood components reentering the construction supply chain. This occurs either as a component in its original family or as a wooden item that has been remanufactured into a new wooden construction component. The component may be undamaged and ready for immediate reuse. It could require minor repairs before being returned to the supply chain. In some cases, it requires restoration or refurbishment before reentering the supply chain. In all cases, the documentation for that item should be updated to show the history of the component. Once the CDW has been selected for disposition back into the construction supply chain, a decision is required to determine which approach is appropriate. This FAST analysis diagram is the ideal state, so no unnecessary functions are shown. If an organization does their own internal FAST analysis, they may discover other unneeded functions embedded in their process.

The second higher-order function is to transform the wooden elements within the CDW into a new state. In this case, the FAST analysis diagram has four primary functions that reflect the four different types of transformation. Each of these primary functions has a secondary function that represents the transformation process and a function that represents the selection process. In addition, there is again the function

Fig. 3 FAST analysis when wood component reenters the supply chain

Fig. 4 FAST analysis when wood components will not reenter the supply chain

of updating the documentation based on the disposition of the CDW wood elements. This analysis is represented in Fig. 4. As with the previous FAST analysis, an organization may find unneeded functions when they do an internal FAST analysis.

4.3 Function Cost Matrix

The FCM combines the steps from the process flow with the functions from the FAST analysis. In this case, there are 21 functions and 22 process steps. The FCM functions are listed across the top of the matrix. Following the QFD model, the functions are prioritized using the 1 to 5 scale. The process steps are listed down the side of the matrix. The steps are correlated to the functions. The low/medium/high correlations are based on assessing the degree to which completing the step in an excellent manner will directly affect the performance of the function.

When prioritizing the functions, the UN report’s assessment of the circular economy “R” principles was used [3, p. 25]. The perceived value is consistent with industry analysis conducted by López Ruiz et al. [16]. They compiled data from 15 studies on circular economy and construction. These studies covered the preceding 15 years and spanned the globe. The UN study placed the highest priority on the complete reuse of the building, but in that case, there would be no CDW. The next highest priority was component reuse, and this study assigned functions that operate at that level the priority rating of “5.” These functions were associated with the immediate reuse of components as soon as the component is removed from the construction or deconstruction site. These items are intact and retain their full technical qualities. The other function to receive the highest priority of “5” was the update to the data records. With the widespread adoption of Environmental Performance Declarations (EPDs) in the construction industry, it is essential that correct records of the origin and use of wood construction components are maintained.

The next highest priority from the UN report was material reprocessing [3]. The functions associated with this were given a priority of “4.” These were functions directly associated with ensuring the wood components were returned to the construction industry after minor modifications. These would be functions associated with the repair and refurbishment of the recovered item. A rating of “4” was also given to the function, Inspection. This function is needed as support for the repair and refurbishment of items to rate the items correctly and reintroduce them to the supply chain. Finally, the rating of “4” was used with all the functions that selected wood elements in the CDW for some level of circularity, regardless of the process selected. The only selection function not included was the decision to not select a wood item for any type of circular processing and instead just send it to a landfill for decomposition.

The third priority level from the UN report is material recycling [3]. Priority level “3” was used with the functions that transform the wood items recovered from the CDW into another material. This included remanufacturing the items for the construction supply chain and remanufacturing into another type of product that is normally not associated with the construction industry. This latter approach usually includes reprocessing the recovered items into another fiber-based product. This is primarily done by a pulp and paper mill factory. The recovered material is used as stock in those mills. Another function is the use of wood components in the manufacture of new composite materials. Composites rely on a matrix or filler material to provide the overall composite material properties. Generally, CDW wood is less practical than new wood for this application because of the contaminants that are often in the recovered wood items [12].

The lowest two levels in the UN report were energy recovery and disposal. Therefore, energy recovery functions received a “2” rating [3]. With wood items from the CDW, the energy recovery is normally accomplished through incineration. The functions associated with landfills have the priority of “1.” Unfortunately, CDW accounts for 36% of all solid waste in Europe, which is an indication of why these functions are so low in priority [16].

The FCM is found in Table 1. The first step in the process, the generation of CDW, is considered a low relationship with all the functions. It does not directly affect any function, but the functions would not be needed if there was no CDW. The next two process steps determine the circularity function to be applied to the CDW. These steps have a high impact on which the “R” function is used. In addition, since they select the function, they also have a low impact on the final result of each function. The “shipping” steps have a low impact on the functions to which they ship the CDW. They must ship the items to the right location, but they do not directly affect the operation of the “R” function. Not surprisingly, the “R” step has a high correlation with its respective “R” function. Finally, the relationship to the documentation function for the “R” steps that return the product to the construction supply chain is high because this function must complete the EPD. The correlation with the other “R” function is medium since all that is documented is the end of the

Table 1 Function cost matrix

Functions	Component fit for Use	New Component Fabricated	Energy Created	New Wood-fiber product	Composite material	Decompose	Data records updated	Component restored	Component remanufactured	Component repaired	Incineration	Pulp/paper processing	Composite fabrication	Dispose in landfill	Component undamaged	Selected for repair	Selected for refurbishment	Selected for remanufacture	Selected for incineration	Selected for paper product	Selected for composite	No use found	Total	
Priority	5	4	2	3	3	1	5	4	3	4	2	3	3	1	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	1	
CDW Generated	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	73
Recover for Construction?	L	L	L	L	L	L	H								H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	333
Sort for Modification?	L	L					H	H	H	H					H	H	H	H						306
Ship to Distributor	L	L					L																	14
Ship to Manufacturer							L	L	L															12
Shipt to Repair							L			L														9
Remanufacture		H					H		H															108
Refurbish	H						H	H																126
Repair	H						H			H														126
Inspect	H	H					M	M	M	M														129
Introduce to Supply Chain	H	H		L	L		H																	132
Ship to Comosite Plant							L					L												8
Ship to Pulp/Paper Mill							L					L												8
Ship to Incinerator							L				L													7
Ship to Landfill							L						L											6
Incienrate							M				H													33
Pulp Processing							M					H												42
Composite Fabrication							M						H											42
Disposal							M							H										24
Create Energy							L				H													23
Create different Product							L					H												32
Create Composite Material							L						H											32

construction life of the wood item. The correlation of the documentation function with the shipping process steps is low since there should not be any modification to the item while being shipped.

The process steps scores are relative scores, not actual cost, or value amounts. They represent the relative value of these steps with respect to each other. The higher the score, the more important that step is to achieve full functional value from the process.

5 Discussion

This analysis is intended to provide a methodology and framework for understanding where value is to be created in the process of recovering and recycling wood from CDW. This framework can be used by those in the market or those intending to enter the market. The result of the analysis is a tool that prioritizes the process steps.

Fig. 5 Prioritized process map for waste recovery and disposition

Organizations can use this tool to identify areas for improvement or new business opportunities. Figure 5 shows the prioritized steps in the process of recovering wood from CDW.

The Function Cost Matrix does not contain any surprises, but it places clear emphasis on several process steps. In this case, the steps that decide what wood items are to be recovered and what “R” process will be used are the steps with the highest scores. This is consistent with the recommendations by López Ruiz et al. on the importance of creating a Site Waste Management Plan and developing collection and segregation techniques [16]. To create maximum value in the context of the circular economy, the two decision steps that determine which wood items can be recovered and identify the best path for circularity must be done in an excellent and efficient manner. That may mean investing in techniques to improve the performance of those steps. Since those steps are early in the process, they are also one of the first points of resistance noted in the UN report [3]. This is understandable. Without clear guidelines and methods for making these decisions, these steps could create delays, added costs, and risk if the wrong decision is made. These two steps should be the focus of further research and development.

The next set of steps with similar moderately high values are the “R” processing steps that create wood products that return to the construction supply chain following inspection. These include the steps of repair, refurbishment, and remanufacture. Equally important to these steps are the inspection capabilities to qualify and accept these items into the supply chain and the corresponding updates to the EPD. Finally, the actual process of introducing and marketing these recovered items is of moderate importance. Each of these process steps is important and adds value to the construction industry. The relative value of each of these steps is very similar. However, if investment in one of these “R” processes results in that process becoming more efficient with lower costs than others, that process will have a distinct value advantage over the other processes.

The low-value steps are the other “R” processes that do not result in the CDW wood item reentering the construction supply chain. Except for disposal in a landfill, these items represent an element of circularity. However, it is not circularity within the construction industry, which is why their score left them with a low rating. Improvements in these areas will be beneficial for a circular economy, but those benefits will not be directly attributable to the construction industry.

Many of the steps in the process are related to shipping. These steps had very low scores because they did not create value within the circular economy. Nevertheless, they can create a great deal of cost. The costs in the shipping process steps should be minimized or, if possible, eliminated. To do this, one or more of the “R” processes would need to be done at or near the site of the building deconstruction. Another possible option to reduce shipping costs would be to create a recovery site where CDW is shipped. That site could do the decision processes of determining which “R” approach to use and have the capability to perform some or all the “R” functions at that facility. This would likely lower the total shipping costs and speed up the process of returning the recovered wood item back into the construction supply chain.

6 Conclusion

The creation and disposition of CDW is currently an issue for the construction industry as it attempts to adopt the principles of a circular economy. Based on value analysis, the most important step in the process of disposing and recovering CDW is the early decision of which “R” path each wood item in the CDW should follow. The highest value paths are those in which the wood item is returned to the construction supply chain. There are four options to achieve this objective, reuse, repair, refurbish, and remanufacture. Investment in the tools or techniques used to improve disposition decision-making or these “R” processing would likely improve the value of the construction wood recovery process. To create maximum value from a circular economy perspective, options for disposing of wood items—such as repurposing, recycling, recovering, or disposing of them in a landfill—should be carefully considered; however, these options may not align with the construction industry’s value priorities. Furthermore, any measures to reduce or streamline the shipping costs associated with the disposition and recovery of CDW should be implemented, as these costs do not inherently add value.

This study was conducted as a qualitative analysis of the functional value of each step in a generic process for recovering and disposing of wood items found in CDW. Further research should be done in specific local regions using the actual costs of functions in that region. The access and capability of different “R” function capabilities could change the scores on the process steps.

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